

Extraction Chromatographic Studies of Uranium(VI) with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acid (Versatic-10)

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A large number of papers have been published on the extraction of metal ions by carboxylic acids¹. There are reports on investigation with C₇-C₉ acids² and commercially available naphthenic and versatic acids³. Uranium has been separated with high molecular weight amine, tri-iso-octylamine, by the solvent extraction technique⁴. The extraction chromatographic behaviour of uranium(VI) on silica gel column coated with Amberlite LA-1 has been studied⁵ but work on extraction chromatographic study of uranium(VI) with Versatic-10, a high molecular weight carboxylic acid, is lacking. This paper presents the systematic studies on the extraction chromatographic behaviour of uranium(VI) on silica gel column, impregnated with Versatic-10.

Results and Discussion

The extraction chromatographic behaviour of uranium(VI) at pH 3.25-6.0 from acetate buffer showed that uranium can be quantitatively extracted at pH 5.4-6.0. Flow rate upto 2.5 ml min⁻¹ during extraction showed the complete retention of uranium in the column. Common anions like NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, halides, etc. did not interfere in the extraction.

Eluting agents : For the stripping of uranium(VI) from the column after extraction, hydrochloric, nitric, sulphuric, acetic acid, mixed acid (nitric and hydrochloric), ammonium nitrate, sodium nitrate and deionised water were tested as stripping agents. The results are given in Table 1. It was observed that the elution of uranium was completed with 0.10 M hydrochloric acid, 0.025 M nitric

acid, 0.10 M sulphuric acid, 0.10 M mixed acid (nitric and hydrochloric acid) and 1.5 M acetic acid. There was no elution with ammonium nitrate, sodium nitrate and deionised water. A 0.025 M nitric acid gave the best stripping, hence it was used as the eluent in all further experiments.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF STRIPPING AGENTS FOR REMOVING U^{VI}

Eluent	Concn M	Peak elution volume (V _{max}) ml	Volume for total recovery (V ₁) ml	Recovery %
HCl	0.008	4	20	43.3
	0.01	4	20	59.2
	0.05	4	16	77.5
	0.10	4	10	100.0
HNO ₃	0.010	10	25	45.6
	0.015	10	25	62.3
	0.020	8	20	74.8
	0.025	8	20	100.1
H ₂ SO ₄	0.01	8	20	63.8
	0.05	8	16	75.2
	0.10	8	20	100.1
HNO ₃ + HCl	0.01	8	20	46.3
	0.025	8	20	60.5
	0.05	4	10	78.2
CH ₃ COOH	0.10	4	10	100.0
	0.05	8	20	37.8
	0.10	8	20	56.6
	1.5	8	20	92.3
	1.5	8	20	100.0
NH ₄ NO ₃	4	—	—	—
NaNO ₃	4	—	—	—
H ₂ O	—	—	—	—

pH values = 5.75

Breakthrough capacity : Breakthrough capacity of the column is the amount of ions which can be taken up by the column under conditions

in question, i.e. the number of milliequivalents of ions which can be retained without any leakage being observed. Breakthrough capacity of silica gel impregnated with Versatic-10 was determined with respect to uranium at pH 5.5 and 6.0. An exchanger bed (0.8×3.5 cm) was prepared with the exchanger (1.00 g). The required pH of the exchanger bed and the uranium solution (1.07 mg ml^{-1}) was adjusted with acetate buffer. The uranium solution was then passed through the column at a flow rate 1 ml min^{-1} . The concentrations of uranium in influent and effluent were denoted by C_0 and C respectively, and C/C_0 was plotted against the volume of effluent (Fig. 1). It was found that the leakage of uranium started at pH 5.5 and 6.0 after passing 22 and

Fig. 1 Breakthrough curve of U^{VI} on silica gel coated with Versatic-10.

29 ml of the effluent respectively. Hence uptake of uranium increases with increase in pH. The maximum amounts of uranium loaded quantitatively by Versatic-10 on silica gel at pH 5.5 and 6.0 are 23.54 and 31.02 mg respectively.

Separation of uranium(vi) from binary mixtures : It was possible to separate 494 μg uranium(vi) from several elements in binary mixtures by exploiting the difference in pH at which they formed acetate complexes. At pH 5.75 Mg^{II} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} were not extracted along with uranium(vi), i.e. they passed through the column; later extracted uranium was eluted with 0.025 M nitric acid. The separation of uranium from binary mixture containing Zr^{IV} , Ce^{IV} and

Hg^{II} along with uranium(vi) was achieved by passing the binary mixture through the column at pH 5.75, where both were extracted and they were separated through selective elution. In case of Zr or Ce, uranium was eluted first with 0.1 M nitric acid followed by zirconium with 4.5 M nitric acid or cerium with 1 M sulphuric acid. For the separation of uranium from mercury, Hg was stripped with 0.5 M ammonium nitrate then uranium with 0.1 M nitric acid. Uranium was separated from Th^{IV} by passing the mixture at pH 5.4; both the elements were extracted. Uranium was selectively eluted with 0.025 M nitric acid followed by Th with 0.4 M nitric acid. The separation of uranium(vi) from Al^{III} or Fe^{III} or In^{III} was accomplished by passing the binary mixture through the column at pH 3.2 where uranium passed through the column with mobile phase while the diverse ion was extracted. Later Al was stripped with deionised water, Fe with 0.8 M by hydrochloric acid and In with 0.2 M hydrochloric acid. Cu^{II} , Y^{III} , Pd^{II} , La^{III} , Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} , Gd^{III} , Dy^{III} and Pb^{II} were coextracted and co-eluted with uranium(vi) under the recommended condition causing serious interferences. After separation, uranium was estimated spectrophotometrically while diverse ions were determined complexometrically⁶. The results are given in Table 2.

Separation of U^{VI} from synthetic mixtures :

In order to assess the possible analytical applications, the proposed method was applied to separate uranium from several synthetic multi-component mixtures containing Zr^{IV} , Ce^{IV} , Th^{IV} , Hg^{II} along with uranium(vi). In almost all the cases, quantitative extraction and separation were achieved.

Synthetic mixture containing U, Th and Zr in different proportions, was passed through the column at pH 5.4, when uranium was first stripped from the column with 0.025 M HNO_3 then thorium with 0.4 M HNO_3 followed by zirconium with 4.5 M HNO_3 . The mixture U, Th and Ce was passed through the column at pH 5.4, when uranium was eluted first with 0.025 M HNO_3 then thorium with 0.4 M HNO_3 followed by cerium with 1 M H_2SO_4 . A mixture of U, Ce

and Th was passed through the column at pH 5.5, when uranium was stripped with 0.025 M HNO₃ then cerium with 1 M H₂SO₄ followed by zirconium with 4.5 M HNO₃. The separation of U, Th, Ce and Zr was accomplished at pH 5.4, when uranium was first eluted with 0.025 M HNO₃, then Th with 0.4 M HNO₃, then Ce with 1 M H₂SO₄ followed by Zr with 4.5 M HNO₃. A synthetic mixture of U, Cr and Hg was passed at pH 5.5, when chromium passed through the column with the mobile phase and then Hg was stripped from the column with 0.5 M NH₄NO₃ followed by U with 0.025 M HNO₃. A synthetic mixture of U, Al and Fe was passed through the column at pH 3.2, when uranium was passed through the column with the mobile phase and then Al was eluted with deionised water followed by Fe with 0.8 M HCl. The elution behaviour of some metal ions in multicomponent mixtures is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig 2 Separation of U^{VI} from multicomponent mixtures.

The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and permits separation of uranium(vi) from commonly associated elements. The separation of uranium from these elements is very important and significant as they are commonly associated with uranium. The overall time required for extraction, separation and estimation of uranium does not exceed 3 h.

Experimental

An Elico LI-120 pH meter provided with glass and saturated calomel electrodes, a Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer, a Dimmerstat 7D-1F hot-cum-cold bath and a chromatographic column (i.d. 0.8 cm) of Borocil glass with glass wool plug at the bottom were used.

Versatic-10 (Shell Chemical), a mixture of C₁₀ isomeric tertiary monocarboxylic acid, was used as the liquid cation exchanger. A stock solution of uranium (6.71 mg ml⁻¹) was made by dissolving UO₂(NO₃)₂·6H₂O (A.R.) in demineralised water and standardised complexometrically with EDTA⁶. Solutions containing 494 μg ml⁻¹ of uranium were prepared through appropriate dilution. Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared from acetic acid (0.2 M) and ammonium acetate (0.2 M).

Preparation of ion exchange material : Silica gel (30–120 mesh, B.D.H.) was rendered

Metal ion	Weight of metal ions added, mg	Weight of metal ion recovered, mg	Recovery of U μg
Mg ^{II}	1.20	1.19	496.5
Al ^{IIIa}	0.70	0.69	500.0
Ce ^{III}	0.62	0.62	494.0
Mn ^{II}	1.10	1.08	501.9
Fe ^{IIIa}	1.67	1.64	501.4
Co ^{II}	1.35	1.35	493.5
Ni ^{II}	1.24	1.25	493.5
Cu ^{II}	1.40	—	—
Y ^{III}	0.98	—	—
Zn ^{II}	1.55	1.52	501.9
Pd ^{II}	1.18	—	—
Cd ^{II}	1.80	1.78	498.5
In ^{IIIa}	2.30	2.32	488.5
La ^{III}	1.39	—	—
Pr ^{III}	1.26	—	—
Nd ^{III}	1.26	—	—
Sm ^{III}	1.34	—	—
Dy ^{III}	1.22	—	—
Gd ^{III}	1.41	—	—
Hg ^{II}	1.34	1.36	488.5
Ce ^{IV}	1.40	1.37	499.4
Th ^{IVb}	1.16	1.18	487.0
Zr ^{IV}	1.39	1.41	500.4
Pb ^{II}	1.23	—	—

pH values = 5.75, ^a3.2, ^b5.4

hydrophobic by exposing it to the vapours of dimethyldichlorosilane in nitrogen atmosphere. Then it was washed with methanol (A.R.) and dried at 100°. The gel was impregnated with Versatic-10, diluted in benzene and dried in a rotary vacuum evaporator to achieve an uniform coating. Excess benzene was washed off with 2 M HCl. In routine work, 1 ml of dimethyl dichlorosilane is adequate for 10 g of silica gel and 1 g of hydrophobic gel can take up about 0.8 ml of Versatic-10. For column operation, 2–3 g of impregnated silica gel was slurried with water and poured into the column. Voids present in the columns were removed by gently pressing with a glass rod. Silica gel was preferred as the support because it is porous and retains a considerable amount of extractant. Each column could be used for at least 25 cycles without any loss of exchange capacity.

Determination exchange capacity : Exchange capacity was determined at different temperatures by measuring the number of milligram equivalents of sodium ion absorbed by 1 g of the dry exchanger in the hydrogen form. In a 125 ml of standard joint bottle, the dry exchanger (1 g) was mixed with solutions of NaCl (20 ml; 2.5 M), NaOH (15 ml; 0.22 M) and deionised water (15 ml). The exchanger was equilibrated for 6 h in a hot-cum-cold bath at different temperatures. The hydrogen ion liberated from the exchanger reacted with NaOH and the excess NaOH was estimated titrimetrically with HCl.

General extraction procedure : An aliquot containing 494 μg U^{VI} was mixed with acetate buffer (10 ml) and adjusted to the desired pH with acetic acid or ammonium acetate. The solution was then passed through the pretreated chromatographic column (i.d. 0.8 cm) loaded with Versatic-10 (3 g) coated on silica gel giving a bed-height of 6.5 cm, at a flow rate of 1 ml min^{-1} . After extraction, uranium was eluted with different mineral acids and salt solutions. Five fractions were collected and uranium from each fraction was estimated spectrophotometrically at 400 nm^7 .

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